

CERAMICS IN EUROPE

2022 Kraków
10th–14th July

ICC9

A B S T R A C T
B O O K

Content

Plenary Speakers 16

Structure and Properties of Zeta-Phase Tantalum Carbide	17
Texture Engineering of Lead-based and Lead-free Piezoelectric Ceramics	18

Symposium A: Synthesis of Powders 19

Highly crystalline boron nitride powders by pyrolysis and mechanochemical synthesis of ammonia borane and alkali metal-containing precursors	20
Transition between two solid-solutions: effective and easy way for fine $Ce_{1-x}Gd_xO_{2-x/2}$ powders preparation	21
Study of heteroaggregation between silica particles modified by polyelectrolyte multilayers	22
Microfluidic synthesis of amino- and carboxyl-functionalized magnetite nanoparticles	23
Powder based on ReB ₂	24
Low-temperature synthesis of nanocrystalline high-entropy oxides and effect of heat treatment on structural changes	25
Stirring-hydrothermal Synthesis of Uniformity Improved Plate like Potassium-Sodium Niobate (KNN) Templates	26
Effects of temperature, aging time, and method of introducing stabilizer oxide into solid solution on properties of Mg-PSZ materials.	27
Preliminary Study of the Cold Sintering Process (CSP) for Geopolymer Powders	28
Study of wet chemistry methods for fabricating potassium sodium niobate materials	29
Copper doped ceria nanocatalyst for VOCs oxidation	30
Low-temperature synthesis of britholite-(La) by sol-gel method	31
Bio-inspired nanoplatelet-like particles of hydroxyapatite	32
Novel MAB phases	33
Synthesis of high entropy carbide (Ti, Zr, Hf, Nb, Ta)C	34
Oxalate salts: From oxide powder synthesis to field assisted sintering studies	35
High temperature X-ray diffraction to study the formation of sodium titanates from spray-dried mixtures	36
Effect of Y ₂ O ₃ additive on morphology and phase composition of zirconia solid solutions	37
Homogeneous precipitation of lanthanide oxalates	38

Symposium B: Ceramic Processing 39

Low temperature sintering strategies based on chemical reactivity and control of interfaces	40
Refining of alumina toughened zirconia composites properties by reactive sintering process	41
Rapid Sintering of Ceramics: A Culprit or an Opportunity	42
Cold Sintering of Functional Materials: A Path to a Possible Sustainable Future	43
Trapping a large surface area into a small volume by SPS	44
Colloidal processing of ceramic-matrix-composites - between capabilities and limitations	45
Direct Powder Bed Selective Laser Sintering of Silicon Carbide	46
Sintering behaviour of α -alumina containing low amounts of kaolinite and auxiliary molecules	47
Ignition of densification mechanisms through applied electric/electromagnetic fields during spark plasma sintering - application to a pre-oxidized copper powder	48
Production and recycling of large REBCO sputtering targets	49
Exploring the potential of Ca ₂ CaO dopant for the stabilization of Tetragonal and Cubic ZrO ₂ nanoceramics as an alternative to Ytria (Y ₂ O ₃)	50
Design and elaboration of Polymer-Derived Silicon Oxycarbide (SiO _x C _y) parts by Stereolithography (SLA)	51
3D printed proton-conducting substrates for hydrogen separation	52
Additive manufacturing of ceramic components by fused deposition modelling technology.	53
Formation and influence of plasma in flash sintering of ceramics	54
Role of atmosphere during flash sintering of NiO/8YSZ composite	55
Gadolinium-doped ceria electrolytes by ultrafast high-temperature sintering	56
A novel approach to processing of doped hafnia ceramics	57

New water-thinnable acrylic polymeric binders in processing of BST/polymer composites	58
LTCC tapes for a new generation of SICER silicon-ceramics composite substrates	59
Effect of physical and geometrical parameters on the stability of flash sintering and the quality of flash sintered parts	60
Fast processing of complex ceramic components by robocasting and microwave sintering	61
The study of diamond regrowth in High-Pressure High-Temperature sintered polycrystalline diamond materials	62
Chemical modification of silicon carbide precursors for Direct Ink Writing	63
Nanostructured rutile TiO ₂ ceramics fabricated by High Pressure Spark Plasma Sintering : effect of high pressure on physical densification phenomena	64
Net-shape zeolite monoliths by bulk crystallisation of 3D printed aluminosilicate slurries	65
Hybrid additive manufacturing for the fabrication of freeform silica glass components	66
Enhancing the geometrical capabilities and performance of functional ceramics fabricated with Freeform Injection Molding	67
Surface Reactivity and Processing Properties of Metal Oxide Nanoparticles for Ceramics	68
Large Scale Binder Jetting of Inorganic Components Using a Geopolymer	69
The investigation of ZnO dopant on flash sintering of 3YSZ: Grain growth with electrochemical reactions	70
Engineering of ceramic oxides microstructures using low temperature reactive sintering processes and Flash SPS	71
Flash sintering of Li ₃ V ₂ (PO ₄) ₃ , a mixed cationic/electronic conductor as an electrode active material for Li-ion All-Solid-State Battery	72
Additive manufacturing-assisted shaping of ceramics with complex shape	73
Using Organic Acids to Densify Ceramics	74
Multiphysic and multiscale investigation of the setting process of hydraulic binders: the case of gypsum	75
Effect of Sodium on phase transformation of alumina	76
Mechanical activation and HIP of ZrB ₂ -TiB ₂ based composites for hypersonic system	77
Paste rheology, photopolymerization and mechanical behaviour of tough ceramics prepared by Stereolithography	78
Fast and high resolution volumetric 3D printing of SiOC components	79
Novel approach to fabricate C/C-SiC by applying additive manufacturing based on the fused filament fabrication	80
Efficient optimization of thermal processes in ceramic processing	81
Homogeneous densification of large YSZ cylinders by Flash Sintering	82
Flash Sintering of Alpha-SiC	83
Printability by micro-extrusion of innovative alumina pastes, based on environmentally friendly additives	84
Ceramic cores for reproducing internal cooling channels in high pressure turbine aircraft blades	85
Investigation of densification mechanisms in Ultrafast High-temperature Sintering (UHS)	86
Optimization of Alumina Toughened Zirconia Inks for Direct Ink Writing Applications: Rheological Characterization And Printability	87
Robocasting of piezoelectric ceramics	88
Pre-debinding processes of alumina parts printed by stereolithography	89
Rapid sintering of 3D-printed parts with exceptional high strength	90
Successful Use Cases of LCM Ceramic 3D Printing in Industrial Mass Production	91
Graded ceramic solid-state electrolytes as an example of FAST/SPS-based research and production	92
Microstructural evolution of Inconel 625 – WC system in different heating condition	93
Reactive Laser Sintering of SiC coatings on Inconel 625 substrate	94
Optimized spray granules for dry pressing by means of slurry destabilization and ultrasonic atomization	95
Influence of paraffin wax addition on rheological properties and printability of ethylene vinyl acetate based feedstocks for fused filament fabrication of alumina	96
Does flash sintering involve plastic flow?	97
Scanning transmission electron microscopy studies of segregation behavior in iron doped strontium titanate.	98
Hierarchical compositional control of ceramic composites	99
Cold or Fast: Sintering of Al doped LLZO solid state electrolyte by cold-sintering and flash-sintering	100
Shaping of ceramic by binder jetting	101
Microwave sintering of zirconia bulk and lattice samples shaped by DLP-based stereolithography	102
The Powder Aerosol Deposition Method – Possibilities and Actual Limitations	103
Hydrothermal synthesis of multi-cationic high-entropy layered double hydroxides	104
Additive manufacturing of high strength zirconia ceramics via digital light processing	105
Additive manufacturing of aluminum nitride ceramics with high thermal conductivity via lithography-based ceramic manufacturing	106
Synthesis of K-b-Al ₂ O ₃ solid electrolyte for battery applications	107
Obtaining high fire resistance, backing material clinker using local raw materials - dolomite, quartz ore sand (Georgia) and production waste	108

Ceramic-graphene composites obtained by slip casting: rheological studies and analysis of possible interactions	109
'Shape strain' in Nanoceramics	110
Influence of temperature gradients on flash sintering onset and quality	111
Discontinuous Powder Aerosol Deposition Method: Formation of ceramic films at room temperature using small powder quantities	112
Capibilities of large single-domain bulks REBCO prepared by TSMG	113
Fabrication of ZrB ₂ -hardened Zr ₃ Al ₂ intermetallic composites by high-energy ball-milling and reactive spark-plasma sintering	114
Flash sintering of BZT-BCT ceramics: tuning the microstructure for properties enhancement	115
Rapid pressure-less sintering of advanced oxide ceramics	116
Microstructural evolution of barium titanate at applied non-conventional rapid sintering	117
Hard ferromagnetic ink-jet printed CoFe ₂ O ₄ thin films	118
Preparation of ready-to-print α -alumina granulated powders by spray-drying	119
Shaping KNN powder by binder jetting	120
Role of Surface Carbon Nanolayer on the Activation of Flash Sintering in Pure Tungsten Carbide	121
Additive Manufacturing of Porous Ceramic Bodies by Extrusion of Capillary Suspensions	122
New hardness model for fine fibrous eutectic ceramics prepared by laser-heated floating zone (LFZ)	123
Novel approach to fabrication of porous polymer-derived SiOC ceramics by 3D printing of High Internal Phase Emulsions	124
Impact of high-energy ball milling on piezoelectric properties of the "lead-free" BCZT (Barium Calcium Zirconate Titanate) piezoceramics.	125
The role of fluoride additives in the densification of ceramics – How does it work?	126
Processing and mechanical evaluation of oxide-oxide ceramic matrix composites manufactured using automated fibre placement	127
Fabrication of Porosity Graded Ceramics by Lithography-based Ceramic Manufacturing (LCM)	128
Understanding the flash sintering mechanisms through the electric current parameterization.	129
Optimization of Si ₃ N ₄ -based feedstock for direct ink writing	130
Effect of printing variables on the voids elimination for manufacturing highly dense bulk mullite-based ceramics via Fused Filament Fabrication	131
Effect of feedstock properties and process parameters on the quality of parts prepared with thermoplastic 3D printing	132
Fabrication of complex Silicon Carbide architectures by a novel hybrid additive manufacturing process	133
Fabrication of dense SiC ceramics by a novel hybrid additive manufacturing process	134
Digital Light Processing of Carbides	135
Synthesis and characterization of La ₂ Ce ₂ O ₇ powder and mechanical properties of La ₂ Ce ₂ O ₇ /YSZ composites	136
DLP-based stereolithography of composites in the alumina-zirconia system: processing, microstructural development and mechanical properties	137
Additive manufacturing of feldspar for tooth implants by layerwise slurry deposition	138
Production of complex shaped MoSi ₂ heating elements using additive manufacturing methods and injection molding	139
Conventional and high-speed microwave sintering of robocast porcelain	140
Effect of microwave heating on spinel formation	141
Development of a New Range of Large Ceramic Tiles in Bla-group Stoneware Technology conforming to EN 14411, with Unique Full-body Ornaments Resembling the Patterns of Natural Materials, Including e.g. Stone or Wood	142
Comparative study of Hot-pressing and Spark Plasma Sintering of cerium oxide doped aluminium nitride: influence of the process on ceramics electrical behaviour.	143
Versatility of direct-ink writing for the manufacturing of lattice ceramic truss	144
Reactive sprak plasma sintering of B ₄ C composites using B ₄ C-Ti-B powder mixtures	145
FLASH sintering applied to porcelain production: Development of Processing Maps	146
Sol-Gel and reactive-SPS: a route towards toughening of alumina with low dimensionality carbon nanophases	147
Optimization of inks formulations for processing dense lithium disilicate glass-ceramics by Robocasting	148
Laser surface modification of Inconel 625 by molybdenum and titanium carbides	149
Spark plasma sintering of Inconel 625 – Ti/Zr mixed carbides	150
The microhardness improvement of titanium alloy by ZrO ₂ particles addition	151
Novel hybrid method to additively manufacture graphite structures by Binder Jetting	152
Development of printing resolution for binder jet 3D printing of cement-based inorganic materials: Implementing in-situ control of binder flow rate during printing	153
Effect of binder flow rate on the product quality of binder jet 3D printed magnesium oxychloride cementitious materials	154
Fabrication of Polymer Derived Mullite Ceramics Made by Pellet Extrusion 3D Printer	155
Processing of Rh-doped perovskite protective filters for selective gas sensing	156
Lithography-based Ceramic Manufacturing of Precise Multi-Material Components	157

Shrinkage-free sintering of tin oxide ceramics – Monitoring microstructure and elastic property changes by temperature-dependent impulse excitation	158
Fabrication of doped β -tricalcium phosphate bioceramics by robocasting for bone repair applications	159
Mass customization, with additive manufacturing	160
Challenges in designing of advanced ceramics and composites obtained by colloidal processing	161
Cathode ink formulation for inkjet printing technology	162
Nanometer structured yttria stabilized zirconia via two-photon-polymerization for powder processing	163
Densification behaviour and optical properties of nano-Y ₂ O ₃ ceramics doped with bivalent transition metals	164
Structure and optical properties of Mn and Cr doped MgAl ₂ O ₄ transparent ceramics with LiOH as sintering aid	165
ZrO ₂ -Mo composites fabricated by aqueous colloidal processing with the use of metallic precursor	166
SLA printed part exhibiting biomimetic nacre like structure	167
Structural, Morphological and Optical Studies of Nd/Er-co-doped Y ₂ O ₃ Ceramics	168
Defect-free drying of large fine-particle ceramic bodies prepared by gelcasting method	169
Analysis of ceramic sintering at the particle length scale by in-situ and post-mortem synchrotron X-ray nano-tomography	170
Upcycling of waste glass in development of FFF ceramic material	171
Multi-material printing of reaction bonded carbides by robocasting	172
Improving the properties of ceramic materials by doping combined with colloidal processing	173
Photocurable ceramic dispersions of different compositions for additive manufacturing techniques	174
Fused Deposition Melting of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Ultra-High Temperature Ceramics Matrix Composites	175
Novel materials and fabrication routes for target components for radioactive ion beams	176
Additive Manufacturing of advanced ceramics by layerwise slurry deposition and binder jetting (LSDprint)	177
Structural Investigation of 3D Printed Reaction Bonded Silicone Carbide	178
Effects of Eu, Y, Mg doping on the sintering and microstructural development of MgAl ₂ O ₄	179
Rheological aspects in designing the functional properties of ceramic-matrix-composites	180

Symposium C: Modelling, Simulation, characterization and digitalization of materials and processes **181**

Fracture behaviour in the vicinity of Curie temperature of BaTiO₃ piezoceramic	182
Are disclination dipoles responsible for high temperature superplasticity in ceramics?	183
The Ball-on-Three-Balls-test: Improving accuracy while simplifying stress evaluation	184
Digital twin of sintering using artificial neural network as constitutive law	185
Rigid body motion of multiple particles in solid-state sintering	186
High temperature dielectric properties of different SiCf/SiC samples at various infiltration levels	187
Dark-Field X-ray microscopy for the determination of oxygen vacancies	188
Can indentation cracks describe residual/internal stresses in Al ₂ O ₃ /ZrO ₂ laminates?	189
Light scattering predictions for transparent ceramics with birefringent grains	190
Structural changes of Al ₂ TiO ₅ - MgTi ₂ O ₅ solid solutions resulting from heterogeneous nucleation	191
Optical characterisation of shrinkage for modelling of drying 3D printed green body ceramics	192
Grain morphology and microstructural evolution during high temperature and high-pressure deformation of a potential optical ceramic: comparison to simulated microstructures.	193
Damage propagation in Silicon Nitride ceramics under cyclic indentation	194
Numerical study of electric field distribution in breakdown strength testing of ceramics	195
Response surface methodological (RSM) model for optimizing erosion response of WC reinforced SiC ceramics	196
Processing variables influencing the relative density of Alumina-Zirconia ceramic materials: statistical evidence learned from the literature	197
Modeling of the dielectric properties in ferroelectric-based composites by a new dynamic finite element method	198
Modelling of Hertzian crack initiation in brittle materials using a stress-energy criterion	199
Computational ceramics engineering utilizing microstructure-based simulation of material properties	200
Raman spectra of ceramic materials from first principles	201
The dispersion and aggregation problems of the carbon nanotubes as reinforcing phase assessed by computer simulation	202
Thermal shock characterization of refractories and ceramics using improved in-situ methods	203
Comparative analysis of BaTiO ₃ ceramics produced from cuboidal and spherical nanoparticles: the role of nanopowders assembly during the pressing step	204

Densification behaviour and optical properties of nano-Y₂O₃ ceramics doped with bivalent transition metals

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Abstract:

Transparent yttrium oxide ceramics can be fabricated using Spark Plasma Sintering (SPS). Doping yttria with bivalent ions promotes the diffusion of ions and densification. Bivalent transition metal ions provide double benefits: they assist the densification and, at the same time, introduce optically active elements into Y₂O₃ bodies. The present work investigates the effect of doping nano-yttria ceramics with Mn²⁺, Ni²⁺, or Zn²⁺ on sintering and optical properties of nano Y₂O₃. A commercial nano Y₂O₃ was mixed with acetate sources of dopants and, afterward, consolidated using SPS at a temperature between 1200 and 1500°C depending on the dopant. The samples were then characterised in terms of the final density, microstructure, optical transparency, and photoluminescence. Bivalent transition metals ions dramatically reduce the sintering temperature of Y₂O₃ despite the limited solubility in Y₂O₃ crystal structure. The influences of the incorporation of dopants into Y₂O₃ crystal structure, charge compensation, and defects formation mechanism on the sintering behaviour and optical properties of fine-grained yttria ceramics were critically discussed.

Acknowledgements:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project FunGlass. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020, research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739,566. The financial support of this work by the projects APVV-19-0010 and VEGA 2/0028/21 is gratefully acknowledged. This research work has also been supported by the Operational Programme Integrated Infrastructure, co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund by the project: Advancement and support of R&D for "Centre for diagnostics and quality testing of materials" in the domains of the RIS3 SK specialization, Acronym: CEDITEK II., ITMS2014+ code 313011W442.